

PLASTIC WASTE MANAGEMENT OF LOCAL SHIPS IN CHATTOGRAM PORT: INSIGHTS FROM A QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

Trisa Das¹, Niloy Das^{*2}, Mst. Farzana Rahman Zuthi³, Sudip Kumar Pal⁴, Susanne Kühlewindt⁵, Thomas Haupt⁶, Eckhard Kraft⁷, Md. Al Amin⁸, Sharmin Rahman⁹

¹ Research Assistant, SCIP Plastics Project, Chittagong University of Engineering & Technology (CUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: trisa.das.td@gmail.com

² Research Associate, SCIP Plastics Project, Chittagong University of Engineering & Technology (CUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: niloydas.cuet@gmail.com

³ Professor, Chittagong University of Engineering & Technology (CUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: farzana@cuet.ac.bd

⁴ Professor, Chittagong University of Engineering & Technology (CUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: sudip@cuet.ac.bd

⁵ Research Assistant, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (BUW), Germany, e-mail: susanne.kuehlewindt@uni-weimar.de

⁶ Deputy head, Chair of Biotechnology and Resource Management, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (BUW), Germany, e-mail: thomas.haupt@uni-weimar.de

⁷ Professor & Head, Chair of Biotechnology and Resource Management, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (BUW), Germany, e-mail: eckhard.kraft@uni-weimar.de

⁸ Research Assistant, SCIP Plastics Project, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: mdalamin2308@gmail.com

⁹ Research Assistant, SCIP Plastics Project, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET), Bangladesh, e-mail: sharmin.urp.2k17@gmail.com

Abstract

Marine plastic pollution threatens our oceans and coastal ecosystems, and shipping vessels significantly contribute to this problem. This study investigates the perceptions and practices of crew members aboard local ships in Chattogram Port regarding plastic waste management. A questionnaire survey using random sampling was conducted on 118 local ships, collecting information on the existing scenario and activities of local ships, and practices towards plastic waste handling and disposal scenario. The findings reveal that 41.5% of ships have waste bins readily accessible for crew members. Although most ships have waste bins on board, plastic waste and other waste are not consistently separated. Regarding waste disposal practices, most ships dump waste on a daily basis, and around 52% of ships dump all their waste in the marine environment. The most common method of waste disposal is overboard, and the findings suggest that there is limited recycling of plastic waste. Marine plastic pollution due to shipborne waste can be prevented by implementing regulations to maintain proper waste collection and separation practices, and providing waste reception facilities for collecting waste from ships. In conclusion, addressing marine plastic pollution requires collaboration between crew members, ship operators, and regulatory bodies. Effective strategies and awareness can help safeguard our oceans and preserve their delicate ecosystems.

Keywords

Marine Plastic Pollution; Local Ships; Random Sampling; Plastic Waste, Questionnaire Survey

1. Introduction

Marine plastic pollution significantly harms the environment and economy, especially aquaculture, fishing, tourism, and heritage. Plastics comprise a substantial proportion of solid waste, as they have been used in a variety of applications due to their generally low cost, lightness, and versatility, which can be adjusted by altering factors

such as resistance and flexibility [1]–[4]. Plastic has been extensively utilized in numerous industries and a diverse array of products since the 1950s. Numerous products, such as cigarette filters, plastic bags, food wrappers, beverage bottles, caps and lids, fishing gear, and various other items, serve as sources of marine plastic pollution [5]. Over time, plastic's emission rate has grown substantially, rising from 2 million metric tons (MT) in 1950 to around 19-23 million MT in 2016. On an annual basis, an estimated nine million tons of plastic litter find their way into the ocean, impacting 3461 species and presenting a significant worldwide hazard to ocean well-being, ecosystems, biodiversity, and wildlife preservation.[6]–[8]. Furthermore, the amount of plastic entering aquatic environments is projected to reach 90 million MT annually by 2030 [9], [10].

Marine plastic pollution can occur due to water-based sources such as the shipping and fishing industry and land-based sources like cities and industrial activities. The pollution resulting from shipping is escalating rapidly. Ship waste primarily comprises operational or machinery waste, cargo waste, and human waste. Crew members on commercial ships produce 1.5 kg of waste per day, while those on passenger ships generate 2 kg daily[11], [12]. Bangladesh's economic growth is significantly influenced by Chattogram Port, a significant maritime hub that contributes to the country's economic growth through its extensive trade activities. It has a 710 km long coastline and a marine area of 40,000 sq. miles [13]. The operational activities at the Chattogram port yield a substantial amount of plastic waste, thereby presenting a significant environmental hazard. Among all the international ships handled by this port, MARPOL ANNEX V standards are maintained, resulting in almost no contribution to marine pollution in the area. However, the plastic waste produced by local ships in the port is especially worrying because it has the potential to contaminate the marine ecosystem and harm local wildlife. Despite the importance of managing plastic waste, there is a lack of comprehensive data regarding the current practices and challenges faced by local ships in efficiently handling their plastic waste.

This study aims to investigate the plastic waste management practices of local ships in the Chittagong Port by conducting a questionnaire survey. The primary objective is to identify the gaps in the current practices in the management of plastic waste generated by local ships. The study identifies the practices or behavior of onboard crew members towards waste collection, separation and disposal, and their willingness to adopt more sustainable practices. By understanding the current practices and challenges faced by local ships in managing their plastic waste, this study hopes to contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable waste management strategies for the Chittagong Port. This will not only help to mitigate the environmental impacts of plastic waste but also support the port's efforts to achieve a cleaner and more sustainable environment.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sampling and Questionnaire

The study utilized a questionnaire survey with random sampling as the research design. First and foremost, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify previous research on marine plastic pollution and waste management practices on ships. Based on the gaps in the literature, this questionnaire survey was conducted. The study focused on crew members working on local ships in Chattogram Port who were willing to participate in the survey. A total of 118 ships were randomly selected for the study. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the responses. Before the survey, all participants provided informed consent and were informed of their right to withdraw from the research without penalty.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Existing Scenario of Surveyed Local Ships

A random sampling method was employed to select 118 local ships at Chattogram Port for the survey. During the questionnaire in those ships, general information of those ships and their waste management scenario were gathered based on the crew members responses. This section highlights the activities of the surveyed ships and their categorization based on different aspects. A categorization of the surveyed ships on the basis of their carrying cargoes was made, which is represented in Figure 1. Within the surveyed ships, 60 ships transport any type of non-liquid products. While, few ships are used to carry only specific type of cargoes. For instance, 21 tankers are found to transport only oil, while 12 vessels transport cement. Furthermore, waste from the KSRM Steel Plant, as well as slag, clinker, cement raw materials, and various other extraneous commodities, are transported using a reduced number of vessels. This is mainly due to the several industries and oil companies that are located on the

shore of the Karnafuli River. Through their own jetties, ships bring raw materials from mother vessels or other parts of the country and deliver their byproducts. This visualization illustrates the prevalence of specific cargo categories, with transportation levels of significance for all products except those in liquid or hydrocarbon form.

Figure 1: Total Number of Ships with Different Types of Cargoes Carried

In Figure 2, the voyage time of local ships surveyed in Chattogram port indicates that 34% of ships have voyage times exceeding 15 days, 28% have intervals less than 7 days, and 27% have intervals between 7 and 15 days. This indicates a mixed pattern of short and medium-distance routes. Furthermore, 11% of vessels have not been assigned a specific voyage time. The voyage time includes the freight and loading-unloading of the carried cargoes. In order to load, unload, or transship the cargo and run the ship's maintenance and operational activities during the voyage period, each ship requires a specific number of crew members. The average number of crew members present in the surveyed local ships from where waste was collected is 13.

Figure 2: Voyage Time of Surveyed Local Ships

3.2 Waste Management in the Surveyed Local Ships

The waste of the local ships is mainly domestic waste generated by the crew members. In order to deal with this generated waste, a proper waste management system is necessary. The data provided in Figure 3 illustrates the availability of waste bins on the surveyed local ships at the Chattogram port. According to the survey results, 41.5% of the total respondents reported that bins are available, while 58.5% indicated that bins are not available on board. Due to the lack of availability of waste bins, the probability of waste leaching into the marine environment is high. Enhancing the availability of bins on the ship can improve operational efficiency and waste management in local ships.

Figure 3: Availability of Waste Bins on Board

The relationship between local ships' voyage duration and their waste dumping intervals is illustrated in Figure 4. It has been observed that a significant number of ships with shorter voyage durations (less than 7 days) dispose of their waste either on a daily or weekly basis. As the voyage duration increases, there is a tendency for waste disposal to occur less frequently. Therefore, ships with voyages longer than 15 days are typically willing to dispose of waste either on a weekly or monthly basis. The graph also displays variations in waste management scenarios among ships with similar voyage times. According to the respondents, not all have a specific dumping interval for waste disposal. Additionally, some respondents mentioned that they prefer to wait until they can dispose of their waste in the deep sea, excluding plastic waste.

Figure 4: Voyage Time and Waste Disposal Interval

3.3 Behavior or Practices Towards Source-based Plastic Waste Separation in the Surveyed Local Ships

Figure 5 presents the waste disposal scenario of the surveyed local ships at Chattogram Port. This shows the fate of all waste, including and excluding plastics. A total of 37.3% of the participants dispose of their waste, excluding

plastics, directly into the water body or deep sea. The generated waste of 10.2% of the respondents is dumped in a landfill or on the shore, which can leach into the marine environment. Nevertheless, the landfill of the Chattogram City corporation, which is used by the Chattogram port, is a bit far from the marine environment. Hence, there is less of a possibility of waste leaching into the marine environment. Around 52% of the respondents dump all their waste into the marine environment. This type of direct disposal or leaching of waste including non-biodegradable plastic waste into rivers or the ocean poses the greatest threat to the marine ecosystem. Therefore, Figure 6 illustrates explicitly a graphic representation of waste, including plastics, based on the findings presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Waste disposal scenario in local ships

Figure 6: Plastic waste disposal scenario in local ships

As plastic incineration mainly affects the air and may not have as direct an impact as plastic pollution itself, it is not included in Figure 6. According to the respondents, 61% and 11% plastic waste end up in bodies of water and the deep sea, while 26% is dumped on shores or in landfills. In terms of recyclable plastic, Figure 7 illustrates the scenario of where recyclable plastics ultimately end up. Out of the 118 participants, 48.7% disposed of the plastics in waterbodies, shorelines, or landfills, 27.2% sold them with incentives, and 22.2% reused them. Incineration of the plastic was selected by only 1.9% of participants, who either burned it on board or near the shore.

Figure 7: Fate of Recyclable Plastic Waste

4. Conclusion

Through a questionnaire survey, this study has identified an existing plastic waste management scenario in local ships in the Chattogram port area. The study investigates the inadequate waste management systems and practices of crew members regarding waste disposal on local ships. According to the survey, around 60% of the ships don't have any waste bins onboard. Additionally, 51.7% of ships directly dump plastic waste in the marine environment. Effective cooperation between crew members, ship operators, and regulatory bodies is crucial in addressing marine plastic pollution. By implementing efficient tactics and raising consciousness, we can undertake vital measures to safeguard our oceans and guarantee the conservation of their delicate ecosystems. In order to further this research, it is essential to evaluate existing regulations and investigate new waste management tactics to decrease the marine plastic pollution caused by local shipping vessels. Additionally, future research would be valuable in examining the impact of educational programs and public awareness campaigns on crew waste management.

5. Acknowledgement

The SCIP Plastics project on which this publication is based was funded by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety under grant no. 67MM0004. The author is responsible for the content of this publication.

References

- [1] P. Rios, J. A. Stuart, and E. Grant, "Plastics Disassembly versus Bulk Recycling: Engineering Design for End-of-Life Electronics Resource Recovery," *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 37, no. 23, pp. 5463–5470, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1021/es034675o.
- [2] A. Carpenter and S. M. Macgill, "The EU Directive on port reception facilities for ship-generated waste and cargo residues: The results of a second survey on the provision and uptake of facilities in North Sea ports," *Mar. Pollut. Bull.*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 1541–1547, Dec. 2005, doi: 10.1016/J.MARPOLBUL.2005.06.021.
- [3] A. L. Andrady and M. A. Neal, "Applications and societal benefits of plastics," *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.*, vol. 364, no. 1526, pp. 1977–1984, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1098/rstb.2008.0304.
- [4] E. B. A. V. Pacheco, L. M. Ronchetti, and E. Masanet, "An overview of plastic recycling in Rio de Janeiro," *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.*, vol. 60, pp. 140–146, Mar. 2012, doi: 10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2011.12.010.
- [5] E. Baker, "Marine Litter Vital Graphics," 2016, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20593.89442.
- [6] J. R. Jambeck *et al.*, "Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean," *Science (80-.)*, vol. 347, no. 6223, pp. 768–771, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1126/science.1260352.
- [7] S. Naeem, R. Chazdon, J. E. Duffy, C. Prager, and B. Worm, "Biodiversity and human well-being: An essential link for sustainable development," *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.*, vol. 283, no. 1844, Dec. 2016, doi:

- 10.1098/rspb.2016.2091.
- [8] M. Tekman, M.B., Gutow, L., Macario, A., Haas, A., Walter, A., Bergmann, “LITTERBASE,” *Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung.*, 2021. <https://litterbase.awi.de>
- [9] R. Geyer, J. R. Jambeck, and K. L. Law, “Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made,” *Sci. Adv.*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 3–8, 2017, doi: 10.1126/sciadv.1700782.
- [10] S. B. Borrelle *et al.*, “Predicted growth in plastic waste exceeds efforts to mitigate plastic pollution,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www>.
- [11] International Organization for Standardization (ISO), “ISO 21070:2017 - Ships and marine technology — Marine environment protection — Management and handling of shipboard garbage,” 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/66930.html>
- [12] Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME), “Regional Waste Management Strategies for Arctic Shipping Regional Reception Facilities Plan (RRFP) and Proposal for IMO Consideration,” 2017.
- [13] H. U. Rashid, “Sea Boundary of Bangladesh: A Legal View,” *The daily Star*, 2004.